

THE DIARY OF THE LAZY

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Annotation: the article is about the lifestyle of a lazy man who transforms him from a lazy man into a hard worker. It has proven to be a great force in the people and society that is causing this change.

Keywords: *lazy, society, labor, diligence, protagonist, land, story, power, village, the rich, wealth.*

The story of the “Resurrected corpse” is unique in the work of Ghafur Ghulam. The play tells the story of a lazy man. The story is about the adventures of a lazy man. The work begins with the comparison of Abu Tanbal with the imaginary and interesting story of the Arabian fairy tales, Alif Layla and Laylata (A Thousand and One Nights), which is famous for its variety of themes. The difference is that in his work, the writer takes the protagonist from a negative to a positive state. The story is based on the diary of the protagonist Muhammadali’s son Mamajon. The work demonstrates the educative power of labor based on the struggle between laziness, which is seen as a stain on society. In addition to the prologue and epilogue, the work consists of six chapters and covers the period from 1925 to 1933. Mamajon’s adventures and his ability to speak in his own language helped the children to better understand the ideological content of the work and increase their curiosity. At first it was easier for Mamajon, who was too lazy, to reap the corn his father had planted, than for the old men in the neighborhood to burn. However, Mirjalol, the rich man of the village, was the reason for his change. The rich man seized his house and half a hectare of land and brought Mamajon to his castle, forcing him to work. Mamajon works because he thinks the rich will die and everything will be left to me.

The structure of the work is unique, interesting, the language is clear and simple. The woman in Mamajon’s dream is depicted as “ red lips like buds, black eyebrows with the continuous wings of a swallow flying in the air, the ends of her

hair as curly as a bell, and her face as bright as a rose”. The woman in his dream was like the rich man’s youngest wife, and he believed that all the rich man’s wealth would remain with him when he died. Lazy Mamajon, who does not even want to walk, does not suddenly become a hard worker. The reality of the time, the glory of labor and heroism, the eradication of laziness, the elimination of vices in Mamajon’s mind, and the influence of the community, a real, clear and vital force caused his transformation. The positive examples of good people in recruiting Mamajon are embodied in the image of Sattarkul:

“My brother Sattorkul took me to the arable land.

“Now, don't go to bed”. You also learned to work a little. You are healed and overweight. Come with me. Reluctantly I started following him. He was plowing. I led the horse. The land was full of people: one was harrowing, one was plowing, the other was hoering”.

Such a lively life, hard work in the field, gradually began to arouse in Mamajon a desire to work. Through this image, the writer promotes the idea of diligence. In short, Mamajon gets rid of laziness and backwardness and becomes a conscious worker. Mamajon, who had previously learned to work, slowly began to learn to write and became literate.

The fact that team and free labor played a major role in his re-education is clearly described. Diligence is a peculiarity that is deeply ingrained in Uzbeks. They never rejected honest labor, but instead regarded it as an honor. For an Uzbek, a loaf of bread he makes is better than someone else's. He values only the wealth that comes from hard work, and he believes that a life built on hard work is beautiful.

The story begins with a description of a lazy man’s lifestyle, and ends with his becoming a hardworking man and finding his place in society. Through the writer’s story, he illustrates in interesting examples that labor is a glorifying force that helps a person understand himself, his purpose in life.

References:

1. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iur5TPKVMFkngJShdGjKS1kewjcz0wp/view>